

**INCOME-GENERATING PROJECTS AMONG STATE UNIVERSITIES
AND COLLEGES IN THE MIMAROPA REGION: BASIS FOR AN
ENHANCED IGP FRAMEWORK**

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Income Generating Projects among State Universities and Colleges in the MIMAROPA Region: Basis for an Enhanced IGP Framework

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Abstract

To alleviate the financial difficulties of the Universities and State Colleges, Income Generating Projects (IGPs) should be strengthened to become more efficient. The college's re-energized or improved agri-business program would eventually help it achieve its aims of fiscal autonomy and flexibility in money management, as well as effectively carrying out its duty as a public institution of higher learning. This study looks into and analyzes the factors and challenges of running an income-generating project in six MIMAROPA Region State Universities and Colleges as a foundation for an IGP Framework aimed at providing state universities and colleges with long-term alternative funding sources. The researcher used the Descriptive research method in this study. This strategy entails gathering data to test hypotheses or respond to inquiries. This research employed a mixed methods approach. School administration has put great importance on sustaining and improving the operations of its IGPs to produce high-quality outputs attained through standard operational processes and active monitoring and planning. The profitability and productivity ratios analysis revealed that most SUCs have attained to sustain their IGP despite the onset pandemic. The data showed that IGPs are supported by the school administration through the allocation of just funds for the IGPs, monitoring and improving production processes, establishing a Healthy working environment for the employees and providing rightful wages and incentives, and achievements, helping IGPs reach target consumers and introduce the products to the market, manage finances through records of the transaction provided and backed by cash in and out flow statement, income statement and statement of financial position. Data also revealed that some IGPs are already self-financed, indicating outstanding financial production management. Further interviews also state that some SUCs have tied up with private and government entities, which helped boost the capacities and Production of the IGPs. This study also concludes that the level of support of the SUCs in terms of Production, human resource, marketing, and finance have attained to a moderate extent; the researcher concluded that the school administration has been very supportive of the operation of the IGPs.

Keywords: *income generating projects, framework, colleges and universities*

Introduction

Academic institutions need more consistency and pressure in carrying out their roles to their clientele when financial support from the national government declines and the actual worth of the budget decreases owing to inflation. One of the most critical issues the SUCs face is the government's decreasing subsidy, particularly for Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), and an almost complete phase-out of their Capital Outlays (CO). This issue jeopardizes the quality of service provided by the College or institution to its clients, notably the students, who are the ultimate benefactors. As a result, in the face of such budgetary limits, the College must begin a significant generation of additional funds to strengthen its operations.

Conversely, the SUCs are developing their resources to become globally efficient, relevant, productive, and competitive, having been directed toward operational efficiency or providing quality education at the lowest cost possible. As a result, the SUCs should make the best use of their resources to overcome some financial challenges and anomalies in carrying out their goal.

Raising school fees and other levies to boost revenue differs from the purpose. Furthermore, deriving a solution from this predicament entails a lengthy procedure that includes public consultations with parents, students, and other stakeholders. According to this viewpoint, SUCs must become resourceful to build a better long-term solution. The establishment and management of income-generating projects discovered should aid in achieving the organization's goal and mission.

Instruction, Research, Extension, and Production are the four primary activities that higher education institutions must undertake, with the latter supporting the first three functions of the College or university. Production, which is the fourth role of State Colleges and Universities, has now become a critical link in the continued performance of the academic institution's three functions: instruction, research, and extension.

The school should strengthen the Income Generating Projects (IGPs) to become more efficient. The College's re-energized or improved agri-business program would eventually help it achieve its aims of fiscal autonomy and flexibility in money management, as well as effectively carrying out its duty as a public institution of higher learning. Such a program will also assist in creating employment opportunities for the people living in its service regions, allowing them to become productive and self-sufficient citizens and for long-term social and economic growth.

Financial restrictions have threatened to impede several state colleges and universities (SUCs). The fact that the national government

has been deliberately reducing SUCs' annual budgets is well-recognized among SUCs nationwide. SUCs suffer financial issues due to budget cuts, significantly impacting their economic viability in a competitive economy. They are also vulnerable to pressures and influences from many other societal forces. One stems from the government agencies that supervise the expenditure of funds, the nature and scope of research, and other SUC activities, notably the facilitation of income-generating initiatives, such as NEDA, DBM, CHED, and COA.

Budgets for SUCS and CHED in 2022. Sen. Pia Cayetano chaired a Finance Subcommittee D hearing on the proposed 2022 budgets of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and the Commission on Higher Education on October 21, 2021. During the presentation, the Department of Budget and Management approved a budget for SUCs significantly lower than the budget for 2021. The planned budget for SUCs for 2022 is P71.19 billion, which is less than the P79.1 billion allocation for 2021. While CHED's budget for 2022 is higher than its current budget of P52.6 billion, many of its initiatives have lower budgets or none.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) requested a budget of P62.3 billion for 2022. However, the Department of Budget and Management recommended cutting it to P52.6 billion, a reduction of P9.6 billion. According to Ferdinand Marcos Jr., this means "zero allocation" for the Doctor para sa Bayan Act, Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education, Republic Act 11448, or "Transnational Higher Education, Medical Scholarship and Return Service, Construction of the Proposed Higher Education Development Center," among other things.

The budget cuts also affected the finances to improve CHED's regional offices, the Transnational Education Program, and Universal Access to Quality Postsecondary Education, which provides free tertiary education. The budget reduction will affect state institutions and colleges nationwide, notably Mindanao.

The bulk, if not all, of the State Universities and Colleges, have concentrated their efforts on projects that generate income (IGPs). The current reductions in government subsidies and RA 8292, often known as the Higher Education Modernization Act of 1997, are two key reasons. The national government's decreasing financing to State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) impacts the SUCs' responsibility to maintain their essential duties of instruction, research, and extension. As a result, there is a pressing need to increase Production as one of its functions to sustain operations. (Capiña, 2007)

The decline in a state university and college budgets, as well as the rising enrollment trend in almost all colleges, including both laboratory elementary and secondary schools, appear to be posing a bleak scenario for the SUCs, which has a limited annual budget and, more often than not, is unable to meet the needs of its clientele every semester. The Higher Education Modernization Act of 1997, also known as Republic Act 8292, is a law that establishes a uniform composition and powers of governing boards, as well as the way of nomination and duration of office of presidents of state universities and colleges.

Reforms, policies, and measures were established toward the end, resulting in new opportunities and societal changes in the country. In terms of operations, they are autonomous institutions. They are also self-sufficient in terms of designing academic programs.

The SUC governing board is the Board of Regents (BOR). Its purpose is to: create a more coordinated and integrated higher education system; make them more effective in the development and implementation of higher education policies; provide their governance a more relevant direction; and the academic freedom exercised as granted by the Constitution (CHED, 1997).

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED), which is responsible for setting and enforcing minimum academic program standards, oversees SUCs. The commissioner chairs the governing boards of all SUCs and is in charge of getting the SUC's annual budget approved by Congress. SUCs' curricular offerings/programs expand over time, necessitating the addition of staff, logistics, and government costs, among other things. Because the government could not fully support all of the SUCs' demands, the government needed to contribute to strengthening fiscal competence. The government pushes state-owned tertiary-level institutions to enter the corporate world to supplement the government's diminishing resources.

The SUCs were conceived the introduction of income-generating projects (IGPs) in SUCs as an immediate response to the government's urgent call to devise and implement resource mobilization and generation schemes that will supplement the College's resources and fill in the budget gap for any relevant expenditure items that the SUCs may incur. As a result, Republic Act 8292, often known as the Higher Education Modernization Act of 1997, was enacted, which specifies that:

State universities and colleges are encouraged to engage in income-generating projects to supplement limited resources and eventually become self-sufficient and autonomous. As a result of the government's funding cuts to public education, SUCs must increase their financial capabilities. The increase is intended in income generation to compensate for the yearly drop in budgeted Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and a zero-capital outlay allocation (CO).

As a result of this Republic Act, Southern Tagalog's higher education institutions have pledged to go into IGPs. The institution wishes to maximize and encourage using its underutilized resources to support and strengthen its principal mission of providing quality education to its students.

Furthermore, the CHED's Long-Term Higher Education Development Plan, which spans from 2001 to 2010, aims to strengthen SUCs by developing active IGPs, allowing them to utilize better their economic resources, such as idle lands, existing facilities, and other

technological equipment.

Research Questions

This study analyzes the factors and challenges of running an income-generating project in six MIMAROPA Region State Universities and Colleges as a foundation for an IGP Framework to provide state universities and colleges with long-term alternative funding sources. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the status of the IGPs of SUCs in Region IV-B as assessed by the IGP administrators and staff in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Profile of the IGP workforce, in terms of:
 - 1.1.1 age;
 - 1.1.2 gender;
 - 1.1.3 education attainment;
 - 1.1.4 number of learning development interventions, training programs/seminars attended (per type);
 - 1.1.5 number of years in service;
 - 1.1.6 specialization;
 - 1.1.7 rank; and
 - 1.1.8 status and employment?
 - 1.2. Profile of the IGPs, in terms of:
 - 1.2.1 number of igps;
 - 1.2.2 number of employees (regular and jo);
 - 1.2.3 types of igps;
 - 1.2.4 assets;
 - 1.2.5 organizational structures; and
 - 1.2.6 years of operations?
2. What is the financial performance of the income-generating projects of the six MIMAROPA State Universities and Colleges from 2017 – 2021 regarding productivity and profitability?
3. What is the administration's level of support for the IGPs in the following areas:
 - 3.1. human resource;
 - 3.2. operations (or production);
 - 3.3. marketing; and
 - 3.4. finance?
4. What are the problems encountered by the IGPs in the following management areas as assessed by the Heads of the Business Affairs Offices and Support Staff:
 - 4.1. human resource;
 - 4.2. operations (or production);
 - 4.3. marketing; and
 - 4.4. finance?
5. What IGP Framework could be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This research will employ a mixed methods approach. It is a method of study in which qualitative and quantitative data are collected simultaneously, examined separately, and then combined. Using mixed methods research to combine quantitative and qualitative data can strengthen and enrich the analysis and findings of any income-generating project evaluation.

Participants

The level of support provided by the administrations on the IGP as assessed by the heads of Business Affairs Offices and the support staff, and the problems encountered in the operation of the 6 selected MIMAROPA Region SUCs' IGPs as considered by the Heads of Business Affairs Offices and Support Staff, the study will be using the six heads of Business Affairs offices and all of their support staff as a unit of analysis identified through total population sampling (purposive sampling technique), where the researcher decided to look at the entire population with a specific set of features. Because the number of people with the particular set of qualities the researcher is interested in is very small, the researcher chose to study the entire population.

Instruments

The researcher chose an instrument to employ in this study based on past studies about IGPs established specifically by state universities. Studies of income-generating programs and projects started by institutions other than SUCs (Alamin, 2002; Orgaya, 2007; and Cruz, 2002) also aid in the design of research questions. The researcher examined the instrument's validity and reliability, improved

and verified by business research, entrepreneurship, and management experts. Six (6) experts and professionals. The computed average was 4.03, interpreted as – More Valid, which means that the instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for the interpretation.

The instrument used in this study is composed of three parts: Part 1 of the instrument derives information regarding the profiles of the IGPs and human resources; Part 2 of the instrument derives information regarding the level of support provided by the administration on the IGP as assessed by the Head of Business Affairs Office and the Support Staff; and Part II of the instrument determines the problems encountered in the operation of the six MIMAROPA Region SUCs' IGPs as assessed by the Heads of Business Affairs Offices and Support Staff.

Procedure

The researcher reviewed the pertinent records of existing IGP financial statements and analyzed and evaluated them to determine the financial performance of the Income Generating Projects of the six MIMAROPA State Universities and Colleges from 2017 – 2021 in terms of productivity and profitability. The essential data used a self-made, reliable survey instrument that was confirmed by an expert and supplemented with an interview and observation. The researcher will review relevant financial statements of existing IGPs, analyze them, and evaluate them. Six heads of the Business Affairs Offices and their support staff will become respondents through purposive sampling. The study will also carry out with the permission of the SUCs' presidents. Table 1. shows the scale utilized in the study.

Table 1: *Verbal Descriptors*

<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
4.6 – 5.0	Attained to a Great Extent (GE)
3.6 – 4.5	Attained to a Moderate Extent (ME)
2.6 – 3.5	Attained to less Extent (LE)
1.6 – 2.5	Attained to a Fair Extent (FE)
1.0 – 1.5	Not Attained (NA)

Data Analysis

The data gathered was treated and analyzed using the following statistical techniques.

The researcher used frequencies and percentages to analyze the data from Parts I and II of the survey instrument. The frequency count will be used to show the number of times the responses in the survey. The percentage will show the relationship between the part to the whole. The researcher used a weighted mean in interpreting the data in Part III. The weighted mean will measure the central tendency of the responses.

Tools to Measure Profitability and Productivity

Profitability Ratio with Formula

The profitability ratio assesses a company's capacity to generate revenue concerning its expenses and other costs involved with revenue generating during a given period. This ratio represents the final result of the company. Profitability refers to a company's overall performance or how profitable it is.

Types of Profitability Ratio

Return on Assets

This ratio calculates the earnings per rupee of the company's assets. A higher ratio indicates that the company is doing well. Formula: $\text{Net Profit} \div \text{Total Assets}$

Gross Profit

The researcher calculated the company's marginal profit using this ratio. Calculated revenue is shown by the data using the ratio. A high ratio indicates a higher profit margin, which benefits the company. Formula: $\text{Gross Profit} \div \text{Sales} \times 100$ $\text{Gross Profit} = \text{Sales} + \text{Closing Stock} - \text{op stock} - \text{Purchases} - \text{Direct Expenses}$

Net Profit

This ratio calculates a company's overall profitability by considering all direct and indirect costs. A high ratio indicates that the company is making a profit and that the company is doing well. Formula: $\text{Net Profit} \div \text{Sales} \times 100$ $\text{Net Profit} = \text{Gross Profit} + \text{Indirect Income} - \text{Indirect Expenses}$

Productivity Ratio

It measures the efficiency of a company's production process. The productivity ratio is shown by dividing the outputs produced by a company by the inputs used in its production process. Standard inputs are labor hours, capital, and natural resources, while outputs of the IGPs can measure sales or the number of goods and services produced. Regarding productibility, the number of units produced relative to employee labor hours or by measuring a company's net sales relative to employee labor hours.

Results and Discussion

The results of this research reveal the answer of the respondents from the questionnaire that the researchers conducted. The procedure used to analyze the data.

STATUS OF THE IGPS OF SUCS IN MIMAROPA

Table 1. Profile of the IGP Manpower

Profile	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	total
Age							
21-30	31%	11%	0%	50%	39%	31%	29.16%
31-40	37%	44%	60%	0%	45%	54%	43.75%
41-50	0%	11%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2.08%
51-60	32%	28%	40%	50%	16%	15%	23.96%
61-70	0%	6%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1.04%
Gender							
Male	58%	79%	33%	50%	71%	59%	64.58%
Female	42%	21%	67%	50%	29%	41%	35.42%
Educational Attainment							
Post Graduate	15%	0%	75%	75%	16%	19%	19.79%
College Graduate	64%	62%	25%	25%	74%	72%	64.58%
High School Graduate	21%	38%	0%	0%	10%	9%	15.63%
Number of Learning Development Interventions Attended							
0-5	37%	44%	0%	0%	19%	26%	27.08%
6-10	42%	39%	33%	75%	52%	32%	43.75%
11-15	21%	17%	67%	25%	26%	37%	27.08%
16-20	0%	0%	0%	0%	3%	5%	2.08%
Number of Years in Service							
0-10	45%	39%	50%	0%	32%	40%	38.54%
11-20	33%	22%	25%	75%	39%	32%	33.33%
21-30	22%	33%	25%	25%	26%	16%	22.91%
31 and above	0%	6%	0%	0%	3%	12%	5.21%
Specialization							
Farming	42%	50%	0%	75%	3%	32%	36.46%
Swine Management	32%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%	12.5%
Driving	10%	0%	0%	0%	7%	0%	3.13%
Landscaping	16%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3.13%
Food Processing	0%	17%	0%	0%	48%	0%	18.75%
Management	0%	0%	60%	25%	13%	16%	11.46%
Information Technology	0%	0%	0%	0%	10%	0%	3.13%
Teaching	0%	0%	0%	0%	19%	24%	5.21%
Fisheries	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	12%	2.08%
Housekeeping	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	16%	2.08%
None	0%	0%	40%	0%	0%	0%	2.08%
Rank							
Associate Professor	0%	17%	20%	50%	19%	24%	19.79%
Instructor II	0%	17%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3.13%
Instructor I	0%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%	13.54%
Admin. Aide I	0%	11%	0%	0%	0%	16%	5.21%
Agri. Tech. II	0%	22%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4.30%
Farm Worker II	26%	0%	0%	0%	0%	12%	7.29%
Canteen Assistance	0%	0%	0%	0%	45%	0%	14.58%
No Rank	74%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	14.58%
Not Stated	0%	0%	40%	50%	36%	12%	17.71%
Status of Employment							
Regular	42%	61%	89%	75%	20%	63%	45.83%
Job Order	58%	39%	11%	25%	80%	37%	54.17%

The table above shows the demographic profile of the engaged and employed respondents in 6 MIMAROPA Universities and State Colleges. The data gathered revealed that in terms of age, the majority of the respondents are in the age bracket of 31- 40 years old, with a frequency of 42 and a total percentage of 43.75 %, which shows that they are mature enough to have the capacity for ingenuity

and the ability to interact with clients in a professional approach. The age bracket of 21- 30 got the frequency of 28 with 29.16 % equivalent of the total respondents. At the same time, 1.04 percent of the respondents are 61 – 70 years old, equivalent to 1 out of 96 respondents.

These results suggest that most project participants are in their middle years. These results indicate that those working on these initiatives are unemployed and looking for work.

Regarding gender, most respondents are male, with a total frequency of 62, equivalent to 64.58 percent of the total respondents, while females are only 34, equal to 35.42 %. Based on this information, men are more involved in these projects because they are responsible for caring for their families. Because food is an essential requirement for everyone, men play a crucial role in leading these income-generating initiatives aimed at reducing poverty and ensuring food security becomes a priority for them.

To find out how far along respondents are in their schooling, the researcher questioned them about their educational background. Qualification levels have a direct impact on the career prospects that are available to community members. For example, studies have found a connection between a high unemployment rate and a lack of educational credentials. Most of them have earned graduate degrees, making them qualified to decide on the rules and objectives that direct the IGPs. People who have completed graduate studies are monitoring the IGP thus, capable of making essential judgments about the strategies and objectives controlling the IGPs's' functioning.

Nearly all of them have participated in training sessions about their tasks. In terms of the learning development attended by the respondents, the data gathered revealed that 42 respondents, equivalent to 43.75 %, have attended 6-10 seminars. On the other hand, 26 respondents, equal to 27.08 percent, have attended 0-5 and 11-15 workshops. While 2.08 percent, equivalent to 2 respondents, have attended 16 -20 seminars.

The data gathered also revealed that in terms of the number of services in the job, 37 of the respondents, equivalent to 38.54 % of the total respondents, have been working in the Institution for about 0-10 years. Thirty-two (32) respondents, equal to 33.33 %, have worked in the Institution for about 11-20 years. On the other hand, 22 respondents, equivalent to 22.91 % of the total respondents, have been working in the Institution for about 21-30 years. While 5 of the respondents, equal to 5.21 %, have been working in the Institution for more than 31 years. This result suggests that most of those involved in the IGP's operation have already acquired the information and abilities required to manage the projects. Employees with a company longer have contributed more to the IGPs.

Additionally, most of the respondents to this survey are in the middle of their careers and are responsible for managing IGPs, which is an intriguing aspect of the data. Older people are more mature and serious about their employment.

In terms of the specialization of the respondents, the data gathered revealed that 35 of the respondents, equivalent to 36.46 % of the total respondents, are engaged in farming, which makes it a specialization. Specialization in Food processing garners 18.75 %, equal to 18 respondents. On the other hand, 12 respondents, equivalent to 12.5% of the total respondents, have specialized swine management. 11 of the respondents, equal to 11.46%, have specialized control. While out of the 96 respondents, two (2) are teachers, two (2) are engaged in fisheries, two (2) have specialized in housekeeping, and 2 out of 96 respondents don't have any specialization.

Regarding rank or position, 19 of the respondents were equivalent to 19. 79% of the total respondents are Associate professors. Seventeen (17) of the respondents, equal to 17.71 percent, did not state their rank or position in the office where they work. On the other hand, 14 of the respondents, equivalent to 14.58 % of the total respondents, are canteen assistants. Also, 14 out of the 96 respondents don't have any rank at all. 13 of the respondent's respondents, equivalent to 13.54%, are Instructor I. 7 of the respondents, equal to 7.29%, are farm Worker II, five respondents are Admin Aide I, four respondents are Agri. Tech. II. While 3 of the respondents, equivalent to 3.13% of the total respondents, are Instructor II. In terms of the status of employment, 44 of the respondents, equal to 45.83% of the total respondents, are regular to the job. While 52, equivalent to 54.17% of the total respondents, are job orders.

Table 2. Profile of the IGP

Profile	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University
Number of IGPs	10	4	5	9	1	8
Number of Employees	16	31	6	24	24	24
Types of IGPs	Agri-based Garments Production Rentals	Agri-based and Commercial	Production and Rentals	Production; Agri-based; and Rentals	Production	Agri-based and non-Agri-based
Assets	-	-	-	Building; Equipment; and Machines and Tools	Building; Equipment; and Machines and Tools	-
IGPs	Rice Production;	Food	Garments;	Catering	Canteen	Lowland Rice

Coconut Production; Swine Production; Broiler Production; Calamansi/Rambutan; Vegetable Production; School Physical Education Uniform; Canteen; Printing; and Dormitory	Production; Canteen; Nursery and Development Projects; and Goatery	Apartelle; Rental of Space; Vegetable Tilapia; and Audio-Visual Rooms	Services; Livestock Production; Work Working; Tarpaulin Printing; Rentals; Food Processing Center Catering; Water Station; Vegetable Production; and Rice Production	Production; Coconut Production; Rubber Production; Livestock Production; Piggery; University Store; Food Court; and Cafeteria
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Table 2 discusses the profile of the IGPs of the 6 Universities and Colleges in MIMAROPA—37 IGPs with proper BOR approval. Of the 36 IGPS, 13 IGPs in agricultural production include nursery, goat raising, vegetables, tilapia, and piggery. Seven (7) were involved in food production, such as Canteen, catering services, food processing, food court, and cafeteria. The other 12 are involved in rubber production. Moreover, marketing services include low land Rice Production, Coconut Production, Livestock production, piggery, tarpaulin printing, a water station, and a university store. Four (4) were involved in space rentals such as Audio-visual rooms, apartelle, and rental space; 125 employees and staff are available in the 36 IGPS in Different universities and Colleges in MIMAROPA. Oriental Mindoro State College has the highest human resources, equivalent to 24.8% of the total employees; on the other hand, Marinduque State College has the minor employees, equal to 4.8 %. Regarding the Assets, most colleges have buildings and equipment related to the IGPS they are operating.

This study's findings are consistent with those of Nyangaresi et al. (2016), who found that schools had a variety of IGAs, most of which were in agriculture. The suggestions were that the crop and vegetable cultivation IGPs were an endeavor that suited the MIMAROPA Region's geographic location.

These results are also consistent with those of Jada (2010), who stated in the study that the main IGPs that various education stakeholders could use in the process of generating additional funds instead of external sources included raising cows, poultry, farming crops and vegetables, baking, piggery, and business ventures like opening shops. Many contemporary scholars have highlighted this (Getenge et al., 2014; Odundo & Rambo, 2016; Nwakpa, 2016), pointing out that IGPs, including crop farming, poultry farming, and pig farming, are preferred by the learning environment as they generate extra revenue for school development.

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF THE IGPS (2017-2021)

Profitability Ratio

Table 3. Profitability of the IGPs in terms of Net Profit Ratio

Net Profit Ratio	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University
2017			65.05%	25.43%		65.68%
2018			58.59%	1.94%		62.22%
2019			15.62%	26.84%		40.47%
2020			5.03%	43.80%		25.29%
2021			60.55%	12.50%		72.02%

The table shows the net profit ratio of Marinduque State College from 2017 to 2020 derived from the net profit and total revenue of its IGPs. The data reveal a relatively declining net profit, resulting in the decline of its net profit ratio. The data shows a meager net profit ratio in the year 2020. CoViD-19 Pandemic that year affected the operation of the IGP. Respectively, the net profit can increase in the following year, 2021, when the government-lifted and loosened bans for health protocols.

The table also shows the net profit ratio of Romblon State University from 2017 to 2021 derived from the net profit and total revenue of its IGPs. The data reveal a sudden drop in the IGPs net profit ratio in 2018, with 1.94%, following a ratio of 25.43% in 2017. Unlike other SUCs, who had a sudden decline in the net profit ratio in 2020, Romblon State University was able to gain revenue despite the onset of the CoViD-19 Pandemic, making 2020 the most profitable year of the past five years in terms of net income—however, the increase in the income countered by the decrease of the ratio in 2021 with 12.50% profitability.

The net profit ratio of Western Philippines University from 2017 to 2021, The data reveals a decline in the net profit in the year 2020 which relatively results in its net profit ratio decline. The data shows a meager net profit ratio in the year 2020.

The Mindoro State University respectfully declined to disclose any information about the financial position of their IGPs. Upon the conversation between the researcher and the said state university, they stated that the operation of their IGPs resulted in losses. This

outcome of the production of their IGPs caused distress and remorse to the academic entity.

The Palawan State University and Occidental Mindoro State College have yet to be very responsive to giving in to the researcher's request, providing only their revenues from the past five years. The entity's data does not suffice the demand for the computation of any profitability ratio.

The IGP's existence has helped to improve the university's reputation. The government and the general public have the impression that the university can raise money to supplement its modest resources by participating in IGPs and is not entirely reliant on government subsidies or allocations. The students might use this as a setting to receive practical instruction in entrepreneurship. They make money while in school, which could assist their families in making up for their limited resources.

Odundo and Rambo's (2013) study on the extent to which school-based IGPs contribute value to the financial performance of the schools, which helps encourage students and staff members, reflects these findings.

The data gathered from Occidental Mindoro State University shows that the school has been very supportive in the operation of its IGPs, where most items in the questionnaire were marked attained to a great extent. The result elucidated that the school administration has put great importance on sustaining and improving the operations of its IGPs to produce high-quality outputs attained through standard operational processes and active monitoring and planning. It also shows that the administration of Occidental Mindoro State College has diligently ensured the welfare of its labor force, where most items under the human resource aspect were marked attained to a moderate extent implying that the school has supported their working sector. That secure, they are cared for and receive just compensation for their quality work and standard-driven outputs. In terms of marketing, the school administration promotes and advertises its IGPs. Managing and monitoring the IGPs under the financial aspect has been extended under the supervision of the school administration. The data shows that the school ensures to produce financial statements, including the cash in and out flow of the IGPs, expenditures, and earnings. This data will give the schools an overview of how to manage IGPs and how much they can earn from each. In general, despite the problems encountered by the IGPs in all aspects of production, the school administration has ways to help manage and maintain the operation of the IGPs.

The data gathered revealed that Oriental Mindoro State College has an acceptable productivity performance. Despite the claim of the IGP administration regarding the eventual loss, the data gathered shows that the school administration has been very supportive of the operations of the IGPs. With the school being diligent in managing and monitoring the IGPs, the IGPs were still able to produce desirable outputs. Regarding human resources, respondents agreed that the school shows their care and respect for each employee by providing them their due wages and giving incentives or rewards when a task is accomplished with great diligence and of an excellent standard. Nevertheless, marketing and misalignment of operation processes were critical factors in the loss they experienced. Still and all, it is with great hope that the IGP of the Mindoro State University campuses regained their financial stability and became profitable once more.

The productivity of the IGPs of Marinduque State College is average based on the result. As shown by the data gathered, the IGPs of MSC receive the necessary support from the school administration. Providing them with managerial support, the IGPs of MSC can comprehend and administer operations plans and ensure to produce standard quality outputs. The school has ensured quality outputs by employing reliable and legible workers. The school also supports its IGP financially. School Funds for the operation of the IGPs are in the budget proposal of the school in each fiscal year. The funds allocated for the IGPs are enough to suffice and be the begging cash of the IGP. The school does not only promote the product of its IGPs, but they are the primary market of its IGP. The IGPs are mostly school-based, with the students, staff, and organizations being their primary consumers.

The productivity of the IGPs of Romblon State University is on average as per the responses in the data gathered. The IGP operations are marked attained moderately with corresponding minimal problems encountered. Respondents have also agreed that the school administration has a close look at the operation and management of the IGPs, ensuring the quality of outputs and services it provides. The school's administration has also been careful and mindful of the needs and dues of their employees. With wages paid on time, ensuring a fair and just working environment for the IGP employees, and guaranteeing goal-oriented and passion-driven competent staff, it gives employees their just benefits with rewards and incentives on well-executed and performed tasks. The school's IGP is also strategic in marketing by carefully planning and posting advertisements with the help of the school administration. Advertisement is a crucial part of marketing. It entails what to advertise on a particular day, how to reach the target consumers, and most importantly, who are the target customers. Despite the low level of market patrons, the data gathered reveals that it did not fail to inform the public about its product. In the financial aspect, one IGP from Romblon State University has stated that they are self-financed. At the same time, the rest of the IGPs of the said SUC was able to attain a high financial performance reflecting how great these IGPs are managed financially and in terms of their productivity. As mentioned earlier, the goals of IGP are to be self-sufficient and self-financed. Looking deep into the context of the data gathered, the IGPs of Romblon State University have attained their goals productively by becoming self-sufficient in their operations and attaining a high quality of financial performance, with one being self-financed.

The data gathered reveals that Palawan State University has been very supportive of the operations of its IGPs. The school administration ensures the attainment of standard quality outputs by engaging in the managerial and labor management of its IGPs. The school administration has diligently allocated resources by funding the necessary processes needed to maintain and sustain the

IGP. Its operations are also closely monitored by the school by examining the processes of the IGP to ensure precise and necessary steps to ensure that time, funds, and human resources are well-spent in the production process. The marketing of the IGP is fair, with the school helping to advertise and reach the target consumers to improve the profitability of the IGP.

Out of the six responding SUCs of the MIMAROPA Region, the Western Philippines University has shown the most outstanding production activities with exceptional managerial functions, comprehensive planning and decision making, and unwavering support of the administration to the IGPs in order to prevent, manage and control challenges that may come their way. Upon the researcher's interview with the IGP Head, the school administration has made relations and connections with private and government entities through tie-ups to improve and expand the horizons of its IGPs. The IGP of WPU has also involved the community livelihood and agriculture sector in their operations. The administration assured the communal benefit of the IGPs by empowering, supporting, and promoting local products made by the community folks out of the resources available in the area. This manner causes a domino effect in both profitability and productivity of the different entities engaged in the operation of the IGP. WPU proved that there is no limitation when people in authority give importance to every single opportunity and aim not only for their advantage but for the benefit of all

LEVEL OF SUPPORT PROVIDED TO IGPS BY THE SUC ADMINISTRATION

Table 4 shows the level of support for the administration of universities and colleges in MIMAROPA to their IGPs in terms of human resources. The gathered data revealed that the statement, “The administration promotes workplace supervision, employee welfare regulations, and ensuring that IGP pay rates are fair and competitive” got the highest weighted mean of 4.39 and interpreted as “attained to moderate extent”, statement, The college administrative personnel are supportive of the projects, and statement, “Wages of student assistants are paid timely.” Got the second highest weighted mean of 4.33 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The college provides for an up to date record keeping of all projects” got the weighted mean of 4.31 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent. On the other hand, statement, “The administration provides support staff for the project whenever necessary.” got the weighted mean of 4.29 and interpreted as “attained to moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists in ensuring that all employees follow the requirements set forth in relevant health and safety regulations” got the weighted mean of 4.28 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”

The statement, “The administration supports the employer-employee relationship, which includes working conditions, grievances, and employment contracts” and statement, “The administration assists in the care of the IGP employees on the idea that if they are well-trained and dedicated to the IGP's goals, the IGP will be more successful” Together with statement “The administration supports with the coordination of proper training and ongoing professional development” got the same weighted mean of 4.26 and all interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists the IGP in retaining good, experienced personnel. Got the weighted mean of 4.25 And interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists in the recruitment of the best candidates to work for the IGPs” got the weighted mean of 4.24 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists the IGP in adhering to current laws and staying current with legal changes and advances” got the weighted of 4.15 and interpreted as “Attained to a moderate extent”.

The statement, “The administration gives workers with the necessary training to enable them to provide excellent customer service,” got a weighted mean of 4.07 and was interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists in the recruitment of new staff and guarantees that each position is filled with the most qualified candidate” got the weighted mean of 4.01 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration encourages IGP managers to work hard for the project by providing perks or incentives” got the weighted mean of 4.0 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration provides training for project-in-charge” got the weighted mean of 3.94 and interpreted as “attained to moderate extent”. While, statement, “The college sends project-in-charge to seminars and symposia related to project development and the like” got the lowest weighted mean of 3.84 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent

Rondina (2002) discovered that human, financial, and physical elements, as well as marketing assurance, influence the growth of IGP productivity. He said that project managers have the necessary personality attributes such as commitment, honesty, and suitable work values and that administrators should urge individuals to work on their projects. In addition, according to Orgaya (2007), for an IGP to be effective, the leaders and members of the SUCs involved must be creative, committed, and well-dedicated.

Table 4. Level of Support in the Area of Human Resource

Benchmark Statement on Support of Administration	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted Mean	interpretation
The administration provides support staff for the project whenever necessary.	4.57	4.17	4.2	4	4.31	4.46	4.29	attained to a moderate extent
The administration encourages IGP	4	3.67	3.6	4.25	4.22	4.26	4	attained to a moderate

managers to work hard for the project by providing perks or incentives.								extent
The administration provides training for project-in-charge.	4.15	4	3.6	3.5	3.80	4.6	3.94	attained to a moderate extent
The college sends project-in-charge to seminars and symposia related to project development and the like.	4.11	3.94	3.6	3.5	4.10	3.8	3.84	attained to a moderate extent
The college administrative personnel are supportive of the projects.	4.73	4.22	4.8	3.75	4.16	4.33	4.33	attained to a moderate extent
The college provides for an up-to-date record keeping of all projects.	4.52	4.39	4.0	4	4.41	4.53	4.31	attained to a moderate extent
Wages of student assistants are paid timely.	4.52	3.83	4.4	4.75	4.10	4.4	4.33	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in the recruitment of the best candidates to work for the IGPs.	4.47	4.17	4.4	4	4.25	4.13	4.24	attained to a moderate extent
The administration gives workers with the necessary training to enable them to provide excellent customer service.	4.57	4.06	4.0	3.5	4.35	3.93	4.07	attained to a moderate extent
The administration supports the employer-employee relationship, which includes working conditions, grievances, and employment contracts.	4.47	4.33	4.4	3.75	4.32	4.33	4.26	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in ensuring that all employees follow the requirements set forth in relevant health and safety regulations.	4.47	4.39	4.4	3.75	4.45	4.13	4.28	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in the care of the IGP employees on the idea that if they are well-trained and	4.36	4.22	4.4	4	4.42	4.13	4.26	attained to a moderate extent

dedicated to the IGP's goals, the IGP will be more successful.									
The administration assists in the recruitment of new staff and guarantees that each position is filled with the most qualified candidate.	4.57	3.94	4	4.25	3.77	3.5	4.01	attained to a moderate extent	
The administration supports with the coordination of proper training and ongoing professional development.	4.63	4.17	4	3.5	4.67	4.60	4.26	attained to a moderate extent	
The administration assists the IGP in retaining good, experienced personnel.	4.32	4.22	4	3.75	4.52	4.67	4.01	attained to a moderate extent	
The administration promotes workplace supervision, employee welfare regulations, and ensuring that IGP pay rates are fair and competitive.	4.63	4.33	4	4.5	4.48	4.4	4.26	attained to a moderate extent	
The administration assists the IGP in adhering to current laws and staying current with legal changes and advances.	4.32	4.11	4	3.5	4.48	4.46	4.15	attained to a moderate extent	
Average weighted mean							4.19	attained to a moderate extent	

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Attained to a Great Extent, 3.6–4.5 Attained to a Moderate Extent, 2.6–3.5 Attained to less Extent, 1.6–2.5 Attained to a Fair Extent, 1.0–1.5 Not Attained

Table 5. Level of Support in the Area of Operations (or Production)

Benchmark Statement on Support of Administration	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	Average weighted Mean	Interpretation
The college helps in product disposal through easy installment or salary deduction.	4.63	4.61	4	3.25	3.96	4.2	4.11	attained to a moderate extent
The college provides for immediate replacement or repair of damage equipment or facilities.	4.52	3.67	4.2	3.75	3.77	4.4	4.05	attained to a moderate extent
The administration	4.57	4.22	4.4	4	4.48	4.4	4.35	attained to a

assists with inventory management, selecting the best production process, and distributing finished items to clients or retailers.								moderate extent
The administration assists in the selection of suppliers who provide supplies that are both cost effective and of good quality.	4.68	4.22	4.6	3.75	4.52	4.73	4.42	attained to a moderate extent
The administration promotes the use of the highest-quality procedures to ensure that a product or service meets accepted standards.	4.52	4.5	4.6	3.75	4.06	3.87	4.21	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in ensuring that goods are delivered on schedule and in acceptable condition.	4.73	4.44	4.4	3.75	4.48	4.33	4.36	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in the purchase of raw materials by entering into contracts with regular suppliers and ensuring that the contract's terms, including delivery, pricing, quantity, and quality, are met.	4.73	4.33	4.4	3.75	4.45	4.53	4.37	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in ensuring that all items are thoroughly inspected upon arrival and reports any issues to the supplier.	4.73	4.28	4.4	3.5	4.25	4.06	4.20	attained to a moderate extent
The administration supports regular progress checks to ensure that production plans are reached — and to take corrective action if difficulties arise.	4.57	4.28	4.4	3.75	4.45	4.13	4.26	attained to a moderate extent
The administration encourages the completion of final quality inspections	4.68	4.22	4.4	3.75	4.22	4.46	4.29	attained to a moderate extent

to ensure that the product meets the required standards.		
total average weighted mean	4.26	attained to a moderate extent

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Attained to a Great Extent, 3.6–4.5 Attained to a Moderate Extent, 2.6–3.5 Attained to less Extent, 1.6–2.5 Attained to a Fair Extent, 1.0–1.5 Not Attained

Table 5. shows the level of support given by the administration of universities and state colleges in MIMAROPA to their IGPs in terms of level of support in the area of operations (or production). The gathered data revealed that the Statement, “The administration assists in the selection of suppliers who provide supplies that are both cost effective and of good quality” got the highest weighted mean of 4.42 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent” “The administration assists in the purchase of raw materials by entering into contracts with regular suppliers and ensuring that the contract’s terms, including delivery, pricing, quantity, and quality, are met”. got the second highest weighted mean of 4.37 and interpreted as “Attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration assists in ensuring that goods are delivered on schedule and in acceptable condition” got the weighted mean of 4.36 and interpreted as “Attained to a moderate extent Statement, “The administration assists with inventory management, selecting the best production process, and distributing finished items to clients or retailers” got the weighted mean of 4.35 and interpreted as “Attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration encourages the completion of final quality inspections to ensure that the product meets the required standards” got the weighted mean of 4.29 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”.

On the other hand, Statement, “The administration supports regular progress checks to ensure that production plans are reached — and to take corrective action if difficulties arise” got the weighted mean of 4.26 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. Statement, “The administration promotes the use of the highest-quality procedures to ensure that a product or service meets accepted standards” got the weighted mean of 4.21 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent” Statement, “The administration assists in ensuring that all items are thoroughly inspected upon arrival and reports any issues to the supplier”, got the weighted mean of 4.20 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. The Statement, "The college helps in product disposal through easy installment or salary deduction," got a weighted mean of 4.11 and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent." While the Statement, "The college provides for immediate replacement or repair of damaged equipment or facilities," got the lowest weighted mean of 4.05 and was interpreted as "Attained to a moderate extent."

According to the CHED’s Long-Term Higher Education Development Plan, which runs from 2001 to 2010, aims to empower SUCs by establishing active IGPs, promoting profitable management of their economic resources such as the most efficient use of idle lands, existing facilities, and other technical equipment. (Miranda, et al., 2016) The administration focuses mainly on one goal when it comes to the IGPS, which is to generate income based on the products produced by the facilities and materials. Little did they know that as the facilities and materials in the Production, the chances of ruining and breaking the materials are highly possible. Moreover, this is where the problem begins. When a facility is not functioning or damaged, more problems are entering, such as in the Production and increase in the earnings of the IGPs. The worst scenario is when the facility is damaged, which may lead to a delay in the operation and Production. Thus, the purpose and aim of the project will be defeated.

Table 6. shows the level of Support of the Administration of Universities and Colleges in MIMAROPA to their IGPs, in terms of Level of Support in the Area of marketing (or Production). The gathered data revealed that the statement, "The college provides vehicles for transport and delivery," got the highest weighted mean of 4.30 and was interpreted as "Attained to a moderate extent." The statement, "The administration assists in determining how and when to advertise, as well as developing marketing programs," got a weighted mean of 4.25 and was interpreted as "Attained to a moderate extent." Statement. "The administration encourages promotional initiatives that inform customers about what is offered, such as advertising, sales promotions, and public awareness campaigns" got a weighted mean of 4.17 and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent."

Table 6. Level of Support in the Area of Marketing

Benchmark Statement on Support of Administration	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted mean	interpretation
The college provides vehicles for transport and delivery.	4.78	4.22	4.4	4	4.32	4.06	4.30	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in determining how and when to advertise, as well as developing marketing programs.	4.52	4.17	4.2	4	4.35	4.26	4.25	attained to a moderate extent

Surveys, observations, and interviews are used by the administration to determine whether a product or service would be effective.	3.73	3.83	4.2	3.5	3.90	4.13	3.88	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in determining which type of promotion is ideal for the product, such as a percentage discount or a buy one, get one free offer.	4.57	3.89	4.2	3.75	3.94	4.13	4.08	attained to a moderate extent
The administration assists in identifying and meeting client requirements.	4.57	4.17	4.2	3.5	4.38	3.93	4.13	attained to a moderate extent
The administration encourages promotional initiatives that inform customers about what is offered, such as advertising, sales promotions, and public awareness campaigns.	4.31	3.94	4.2	3.75	4.48	4.33	4.17	attained to a moderate extent
The administration aids in the monitoring of the website's popularity and the gathering of data about its users.	4.63	3.67	4.2	3.5	4.19	4.46	4.11	attained to a moderate extent
Total average weighted mean							4.13	attained to a moderate extent

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Attained to a Great Extent, 3.6–4.5 Attained to a Moderate Extent, 2.6–3.5 Attained to less Extent, 1.6–2.5 Attained to a Fair Extent, 1.0–1.5 Not Attained

On the other hand, the statement, "The administration assists in identifying and meeting client requirements," got a weighted mean of 4.13 and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent." The statement, "The administration aids in the monitoring of the website's popularity and the gathering of data about its users," got a weighted mean of 4.11 and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent." The statement, "The administration assists in determining which type of promotion is ideal for the product, such as a percentage discount or a buy one, get one free offer," got a weighted mean of 4.08 and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent." While the administration uses the statement, "Surveys, observations, and interviews to determine whether a product or service would be effective," it got the lowest weighted mean of 3.88. It was "attained to a moderate extent."

One way to sell products quickly is by giving options to the patrons through delivery or pick up; by this, the administration can avoid any delay in the transaction; any delay in the transaction can cause chaos to the management and the whole project. Regarding product assessment, this is a less priority to the management. Despite the less attention to product assessment, the Universities and Colleges in MIMAROPA are succeeding in their IGPS.

Table 7. Level of Support in the Area of Finance

Benchmark Statement on Support of Administration	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted mean	interpretation
The budget of IGP is timely received accordingly.	4.47	3.5	4.4	4	4.45	4.13	4.16	Attained to moderate extent
Supplementary budget is allowed from college's general fund.	4.31	3.56	4.6	4	4.58	4.06	4.19	Attained to moderate extent
Incentives for project	4	2.83	4.4	4.33	4.10	3.93	3.93	Attained to

implementers & staff are given regularly.									moderate extent
The administration provides budget/capitalization for the IGP.	4.52	4.11	4.4	4.33	4.48	3.67	4.25		Attained to moderate extent
The college provides for immediate release of requested budget for project use base on order priority.	4.63	4	4.4	4	4.39	4.2	4.27		Attained to moderate extent
The college provides for an up-to-date record keeping of all projects.	4.89	4.22	4.4	4.33	4.35	3.8	4.33		Attained to moderate extent
The administration assists an IGP in meeting his or her financial obligations.	4.63	4.17	4.4	4	4.19	4.13	4.25		Attained to moderate extent
The administration wants people to plan ahead so they know how much money will be coming in and out of the IGP.	4.15	4.5	4.2	4.67	4.32	4.2	4.34		Attained to moderate extent
Every year, the university/college presents a Balance Sheet and Profit and Loss Account, as well as a cash flow statement in most cases.	4.63	4.5	4.2	4	4.52	4.26	4.35		Attained to moderate extent
total average weighted mean							4.23		Attained to moderate extent

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Attained to a Great Extent, 3.6–4.5 Attained to a Moderate Extent, 2.6–3.5 Attained to less Extent, 1.6–2.5 Attained to a Fair Extent, 1.0–1.5 Not Attained

Table shows the level of Support of the Administration of Universities and Colleges in MIMAROPA to their IGPs, s in the Area of Finance. The gathered data revealed that the Statement, “Every year, the university/college presents a Balance Sheet and Profit and Loss Account, as well as a cash flow statement in most cases”, got the highest weighted mean of 4.35 and was interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. The Statement, “The administration wants people to plan so they know how much money will be coming in and out of the IGP,” got a weighted mean of 4.35 and was interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent.” Statement, “The college provides for an up-to-date record keeping of all projects,” got the weighted mean of 4.33 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent.” On the other hand, Statement, “The college provides for the immediate release of requested budget for project use base on order priority” with the weighted mean of 4.27 and interpreted as “Attained to a moderate extent.” Statement, “The administration provides budget/capitalization for the IGP” and Statement, “The administration assists an IGP in meeting his or her financial obligations” got the same weighted mean of 4.25. Both are “attained to a moderate extent.” Statement, “Supplementary budget is allowed from college’s general fund” got a weighted mean of 4.19 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”. The Statement, “The budget of IGP is timely received accordingly,” got a weighted mean of 4.16 and was interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent.” While, Statement, “Incentives for project implementers & staff regularly,” got a weighted mean of 3.93 and was interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent.”

The financial performance of a company is measured by how much better off the shareholder is at the end of a period than he was at the start, and this can be determined using ratios derived from financial statements, primarily the balance sheet and income statement, or by using data on stock market prices (Baraza, 2014).

While the statement, "Incentives for project implementers & staff regularly received," got the weighted mean of three points ninety-three and was interpreted as "attained to a moderate extent." IGPs to assist in collecting cash for such initiatives and projects near the finish. One of them stems from the specific requirements for subsidizing sources from government agencies such as NEDA, DBM, CHED, and COA, which regulate the use of assets, the form and scope of research, and other SUC activities that specifically support income-generating initiatives (Villarino, 2016).

Table 8. Summary of Level of Support to the IGPs

Areas	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted mean	Interpretation
Human Resource	4.17	4.19	4.11	3.9	4.28	3.75	4.19	attained to a moderate extent
Operations (or Production)	4.63	4.23	4.38	3.7	4.26	4.31	4.26	attained to a moderate extent
Marketing	4.44	3.98	4.22	3.71	4.22	4.27	4.13	attained to a moderate extent
Finance	4.47	3.93	4.37	4.18	4.38	4.04	4.23	attained to a moderate extent
Total Average weighted Mean							4.17	attained to a moderate extent

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Attained to a Great Extent, 3.6–4.5 Attained to a Moderate Extent, 2.6–3.5 Attained to less Extent, 1.6–2.5 Attained to a Fair Extent, 1.0–1.5 Not Attained

Table 8. shows the summary of level of support from Universities and State Colleges in MIMAROPA to the IGPs. The data gathered revealed that the operation and production areas got the highest average weighted mean of 4.26 and “attained to a moderate extent.” The area of finance got the second highest average of 4.23. It is “attained to a moderate extent.” On the other hand, human resource area got the average weighted mean of 4.19 and interpreted as “attained to a moderate extent”.

Rondina (2002) argued that personality attributes are crucial to the success of an income-generating endeavor as evidence for the findings. A project can be profitable if the management supports it and the workers have the proper work values and attitudes. The project manager requires a positive mindset and positive thinking in order to be motivated and act appropriately.

The results corroborated Orgaya's (2007) study, which found that for IGP to be successful, leaders and SUC participants must be innovative, dedicated, well-motivated, and supportive of all entrepreneurial endeavors. According to Rondina's study from 2002, project managers should encourage employees to complete their work.

PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY THE IGPS

Table 9. shows the Problems Encountered by the Universities and State Colleges in MIMAROPA in the Area of Human Resources to their IGPs. The data gathered revealed that the statement, "Dissatisfaction with the job or the firm when people leave for legitimate reasons, such as moving to another location or being promoted elsewhere," got the highest weighted mean of 2.90 and was interpreted as "Neither agree nor disagree." The statement, "The administration grants o monetary incentives & moral support to the project-in-charge," got a weighted mean of 2.59 and was interpreted as "Neither agree nor disagree." The statement, "Miscommunication between personnel occurs," got a weighted mean of 2.49 and was interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "The laborers lack the needed technical skills," got a weighted mean of 2.47 and was interpreted as "Disagree."

On the other hand, the statement, "The manpower resources are inadequate; there are no staff associations at the university or institution that monitor and communicate staff perspectives and conditions," together with the statement, "The administration does not communicate with employee associations/organizations, does not keep them aware of changes and developments, and does not participate in management negotiations" and the statement "The manpower resources are inadequate" this four statement got the same weighted mean of 2.46 and interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "New workers do not participate in an induction program that informs them about the IGP, their rights and obligations as employees, IGP laws, and the needs of their new position," got a weighted mean of 2.37 and was interpreted as "disagree." The statement, "The project-in-charge is unmotivated due to lack of recognition for his work," and stated, "The administration does not motivate people to do work in their respective projects" got a weighted of 2.34 and interpreted as "Disagree" while stating, "The project-in-charge lack personalities traits like commitment, honesty, and proper work values" got the lowest weighted mean of 2.23 and interpreted as "Disagree."

Table 9. Problems Encountered in the Area of Human Resource

Problems Encountered in IGPs	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	Average weighted mean	Interpretation
The manpower resources are inadequate.	1.79	3.61	3.6	2.75	1.90	1.73	2.46	Disagree
The laborers lack the needed	1.89	3.33	3.8	2	1.97	1.8	2.47	Disagree

technical skills.									
The project-in-charge is unmotivated due to lack of recognition for his work.	1.63	3.17	3.6	1.75	2.06	1.8	2.34	Disagree	
The project-in-charge lack personality traits like commitment, honesty, and proper work values.	1.63	2.94	3.6	1.75	1.83	1.6	2.23	Disagree	
Miscommunication between personnel occurs.	1.79	3.44	3.8	2.5	1.70	1.46	2.49	Disagree	
The administration grants o monetary incentives & moral support to project-in-charge.	1.42	3.56	3.8	2	2.93	1.8	2.34	neither Agree nor disagree	
The administration does not motivate people to do work in their respective projects.	1.58	3.39	3.6	2	2.16	1.33	2.37	Disagree	
New workers do not participate in an induction program that informs them about the IGP, their rights and obligations as employees, IGP laws, and the needs of their new position.	1.53	3.61	3.6	2.25	1.90	1.4	2.90	Disagree	
Dissatisfaction with the job or the firm isn't probed when people leave for legitimate reasons, such as moving to another location or being promoted elsewhere.	1.84	3.39	3.8	2.5	2.45	3.4	2.46	neither Agree nor disagree	
There are no staff associations at the university or institution that monitor and communicate staff perspectives and conditions.	1.58	3.39	3.6	2.5	1.97	1.73	2.46	Disagree	
The administration does not communicate with employee associations/organizations, does not keep them aware of changes and developments, and does not participate in management negotiations. the man power resources are inadequate	1.74	3.39	4.0	2.5	1.81	1.33	2.46	Disagree	
Total average weighted mean							2.46	Disagree	

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Strongly agree, 3.6–4.5 Agree, 2.6–3.5 Neither agree nor disagree, 1.6–2.5 Disagree, 1.0–1.5 Strongly Disagree

The Philippines is fortunate to have abundant human resources; however, these resources are only sometimes wholly used. For greener pastures, most experts prefer to work outside of the country. The Philippines has experienced a "brain drain" on occasion. Most professionals work abroad to increase their take-home earnings and provide a better future for their families. Encouraging people to enter IGPs will result in higher remuneration for workers due to the added income.

Rondina (2002) said that project managers have the necessary personality attributes such as commitment, honesty, and suitable work values and that administrators should urge individuals to work on their projects. In addition, according to Orgaya (2007), for an IGP to be effective, the leaders and members of the SUCs involved must be creative, committed, and well-dedicated.

Table 10. Problems Encountered in the Area of Operations (or Production)

Problems Encountered in IGPs	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average Weighted Mean	Interpretation
The project-in-charge encounters difficulty in timely acquisition of project inputs/materials.	2.21	4.28	4.6	3	1.51	1.53	2.86	Neither agree nor Disagree
The laborers do not	1.31	3.28	3.6	2.25	1.35	1.86	2.28	Disagree

perform well in their assigned tasks.									
Starting with the raw materials, quality isn't 'built-in' at every level of the process.	1.57	3.17	3.6	2.25	1.77	1.73	2.35	Disagree	
The materials are not obtained at a reasonable cost.	1.84	3.44	3.6	2.25	1.61	2	2.46	Disagree	
Raw materials are not kept in a separate area near the production area.	1.68	3.44	3.6	2	1.45	1.53	2.28	Disagree	
The manufacturing process is not mechanized.	1.53	3.44	3.6	2.25	1.58	1.6	2.33	Disagree	
This indicates that machines or robots are not capable of doing all ordinary or dangerous tasks.	1.89	3.78	3.8	2.25	1.09	1.66	2.41	Disagree	
Operator teams do not collaborate and take responsibility for a series of operations.	1.32	3.44	3.6	1.75	1.77	1.33	2.20	Disagree	
The university/college lacks a maintenance plan that specifies when machines will be out of service for inspection and maintenance.	1.62	3.22	3.6	2.25	1.90	1.73	2.39	Disagree	
The administration is not focused on ensuring that all employees are working effectively and efficiently and that their efforts are focused on important production areas and targets.	1.47	2.83	3.6	2.25	2	1.6	2.29	Disagree	
Total Average weighted mean							2.39	Disagree	

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Strongly agree, 3.6–4.5 Agree, 2.6–3.5 Neither agree nor disagree, 1.6–2.5 Disagree, 1.0–1.5 Strongly Disagree

Table 10. shows the Problems Encountered by the Universities and State Colleges in MIMAROPA in the Area of Operations (or Production) to their IGPs. The data gathered revealed that the statement, "The project-in-charge encounters difficulty in timely acquisition of project inputs/materials." got a weighted mean of 2.86 and interpreted it as "Neither agree nor disagree." The statement, "The materials are not obtained at a reasonable cost," got a weighted mean of 2.46, interpreted as "Disagree." The statement "This indicates that machines or robots are incapable of doing all ordinary or dangerous tasks" got a weighted mean of 2.41 and was interpreted as "Disagree."

On the other hand, the statement, "The university/college lacks a maintenance plan that specifies when machines will be out of service for inspection and maintenance," got a weighted mean of 2.39 and was interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "Starting with the raw materials, quality is not 'built-in' at every level of the process," got a weighted mean of 2.35 and was interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "The manufacturing process is not mechanized," got a weight of 2.33 and was interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "The administration is not focused on ensuring that all employees are working effectively and efficiently and that their efforts are focused on important production areas and targets," got a weighted mean of 2.29 and was interpreted as "Disagree." The statement, "The laborers do not perform well in their assigned tasks" and stated, "Raw materials are not for production kept in a separate area near the production area" got a weighted mean of 2.28, and both were interpreted as "Disagree." While the statement, "Operator teams do not collaborate and take responsibility for a series of operations," got the lowest weighted mean of 2.20 and was interpreted as "Disagree."

IGPs, on the other hand, face problems typical in SUCs. According to stakeholders and administrators in State Universities and Colleges, the national subsidy for MOOE is progressively reducing, aiming that SUCs may turn to IGP implementation to supplement their minimal income.

Table 11. Problems Encountered in the Area of Marketing

Problems Encountered in IGPs	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted Mean	Interpretation
Lack of market and patrons.	1.79	2.56	3.6	3.5	2.48	1.93	2.62	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Customers are rarely informed about products via advertisements for goods and services.	1.84	3.72	3.6	2.5	2	1.73	2.57	Neither Agree nor Disagree
From the production worker who must manufacture high-quality goods to the accounts clerk who must reply to a customer enquiry swiftly and accurately, some IGP office personnel are not trained to put the client first.	1.32	3.22	3.8	2.5	2.29	1.53	2.44	Disagree
Customers' wants aren't met by developing (or adapting) products or providing services.	1.68	3.56	3.4	2.25	1.90	1.8	2.43	Disagree
The office website is not kept up to date by the staff.	1.74	3.28	3.8	2.25	1.48	1.67	2.37	Disagree
Total average weighted mean							2.49	Disagree

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Strongly agree, 3.6–4.5 Agree, 2.6–3.5 Neither agree nor disagree, 1.6–2.5 Disagree, 1.0–1.5 Strongly Disagree

Table 11. shows the Problems Encountered by the Universities and State Colleges in MIMAROPA in the Area of Marketing to their IGPs. The data gathered revealed that the Statement, "Lack of market and patrons," got the weighted mean of 2.62 and was interpreted as "Neither agree nor disagree." The Statement, "Customers are rarely informed about products via advertisements for goods and services," got a weight of 2.57 and was interpreted as "Neither agree nor disagree." On the other hand, the Statement, "From the production worker who must manufacture high-quality goods to the accounts clerk who must reply to a customer inquiry swiftly and accurately, some IGP office personnel are not trained to put the client first" got the weighted mean of 2.44 and interpreted as "Disagree." The Statement, "Customers' wants are not met by developing (or adapting) products or providing services," got a weighted mean of 2.43 and was interpreted as "Disagree." While, Statement, "The office website is not kept up to date by the staff," got a weighted mean of 2.37 and was interpreted as "Disagree."

There are times when the product that the IGPs produce does not suit the needs of the community. When the pandemic struck, most of the Production of the IGPS stopped. These mean a lot to the Production and the, profitability and productivity of the IGPS, particularly in 6 universities and colleges of MIMAROPA. Sometimes the product is sold outside the community; the product must be delivered outside the province to continue the operation of the IGPS. Modern technologies, particularly social media, play a significant role in the promotion of some products of the IGPS. Patrons can easily purchase products by simply browsing the internet. It is another form of advertising and promoting the product. According to (Florendo, 2005), real income-generating ventures must be viable or visible. When consumers view samples of items in TESDA Trade Schools, it is simpler to disseminate information and technology.

Table 12. Problems Encountered in the Finance

Problems Encountered in IGPs	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	average weighted Mean	Interpretation
Inadequate funds allocated for the project	1.47	3.72	2.2	3	1.90	1.88	2.36	Disagree
Gov't accounting procedures & practices affect the timely acquisition of budget & inputs.	2	4	2.0	3	2.22	1.26	2.41	Disagree

All IGPs do not require final accounting to determine how much profit or loss has been made and how much the IGP is worth.	1.32	3.5	2.2	3	1.83	1.73	2.26	Disagree
IGP employees do not keep track of every money earned and spent so that the heads always know how much profit (or loss) each product or portion of the IGP is making and how much money the IGP has on hand.	1.36	3.44	2.2	3.5	1.64	1.54	2.28	Disagree
Accountants do not keep track of budgets and actual sales revenue, produce cash flow predictions, or specialize in analyzing daily financial data and keeping management informed.	1.53	3.17	2.4	3	1.61	1.11	2.14	Disagree
Statutory accounts are not prepared by accountants.	1.58	3.06	2.4	2.5	1.71	1.15	2.07	Disagree
Overdue payments are not monitored, and no action is taken to reclaim bad debts.	1.37	3.22	2.6	3	1.77	1.12	2.18	Disagree
IGP employees do not assist the accountants by maintaining financial records, pursuing late payments, or paying for products acquired.	1.53	3.22	2.6	3	1.61	1.85	2.30	Disagree
IGPs do not utilize spreadsheets to analyze financial data or computer accounting packages to record financial transactions and produce their accounts.	1.63	3.22	2.4	2.75	1.83	1.39	2.20	Disagree
IGPs require funds to achieve specified goals and objectives related to expansion, growth, or simply replacing equipment and machinery.	1.84	3.83	2.0	4	3.16	1.42	2.71	Neither agree nor Disagree
Total Average weighted Mean				2.29				Disagree

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Strongly agree, 3.6–4.5 Agree, 2.6–3.5 Neither agree nor disagree, 1.6–2.5 Disagree, 1.0–1.5 Strongly Disagree

The data gathered revealed that the Statement, “IGPs require funds to achieve specified goals and objectives related to expansion, growth, or simply replacing equipment and machinery,” got a weighted mean of 2.71 and interpreted as “Neither agree nor disagree.” Statement, “Gov’t accounting procedures & practices affect the timely acquisition of budget & inputs” got the weighted mean of 2.41 and interpreted as “disagree”. Statement, “Inadequate funds allocated for the project” got the weighted mean of 2.36 and interpreted as “disagree”. On the other hand, the Statement, “IGP employees do not assist the accountants by maintaining financial records, pursuing late payments, or paying for products acquired,” got a weighted mean of 2.30 and was interpreted as “Disagree.” Statement, “IGP employees do not keep track of every money earned and spent so that the heads always know how much profit (or loss) each product

or portion of the IGP is making and how much money the IGP has on hand” got the weighted mean of 2.28 and interpreted as “Disagree”. Statement, “All IGPs do not require final accounting to determine how much profit or loss has been made and how much the IGP is worth”, got the weighted mean of 2.26 and interpreted as “disagree”.

Statement, “IGPs do not utilize spreadsheets to analyze financial data or computer accounting packages to record financial transactions and produce their accounts” got the weighted mean of 2.20 and interpreted as “Disagree”. Statement, “Overdue payments are not monitored, and no action is taken to reclaim bad debts” got the weighted mean of 2.18 and interpreted as “disagree”. Statement, “Accountants do not keep track of budgets and actual sales revenue, produce cash flow predictions, or specialize in analyzing daily financial data and keeping management informed” got the weighted mean of 2.14 and interpreted as “Disagree”. While, Statement, “Statutory accounts are not prepared by accountants” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.07 and interpreted as “Disagree”.

According to (TESDA-CLSU Guidebook on IGP, the school's budget was augmented with IGPs. The income is utilized to recruit more project staff, buy supplies, materials, and equipment, and develop teaching, research, extension, training, and productive operations facilities. The program has an allotted budget.

Table 13. Summary of Problems Encountered by the IGPs

Areas	Mindoro State University	Occidental Mindoro State College	Marinduque State College	Romblon State University	Palawan State University	Western Philippines University	weighted mean	interpretation
Human Resource	1.67	3.38	3.71	2.23	2.06	1.81	2.46	Disagree
Operations (or Production)	1.64	3.43	3.72	2.25	1.60	1.66	2.39	Disagree
Marketing	1.67	3.2	4.4	2.6	2.03	1.73	2.49	Disagree
Finance	1.56	3.44	2.3	3.08	1.93	1.45	2.29	Disagree
Total Average weighted Mean							2.40	Disagree

Legend: 4.6–5.0 Strongly agree, 3.6–4.5 Agree, 2.6–3.5 Neither agree nor disagree, 1.6–2.5 Disagree, 1.0–1.5 Strongly Disagree

The table above summarizes the Problems Encountered by the universities and State Colleges in MIMAROPA. The data gathered revealed that the marketing area got the highest average weighted mean of 2.49, interpreted as “Disagree.” The human resource area got an average weighted mean of 2.46 and was interpreted as “Disagree.” The area of operation or production got an average weighted mean of 2.39 and was interpreted as “Disagree.” While the finance area got the lowest average weighted mean of 2.29 and was interpreted as “Disagree.”

Conclusion

This study concludes that in terms of profitability and productivity ratios, analysis revealed that most SUCs have attained to sustain their IGP despite the onset pandemic. The data also revealed that IGPs are supported by the school administration through the allocation of just funds for the IGPs, monitoring and improving production processes, establishing a healthy working environment for the employees and providing rightful wages and incentives.

Data also revealed that some IGPs are already self-financed, indicating outstanding financial production management. Further interviews also state that some SUCs have tied up with private and government entities, which helped boost the capacities and Production of the IGPs.

This study also concludes that the level of support of the SUCs in Production, human resource, marketing, and finance have attained to a moderate extent; the school administration has been very supportive of the operation of the IGPs. This study also concludes that the project-in-charge encounters difficulty in the timely acquisition of project inputs/materials. Gov't accounting procedures & practices affect the timely acquisition of budgets & inputs in humans.

Therefore, despite the success of IGPs, there are still problems with their implementation of the IGPs. The researcher formulated the following recommendations after analyzing the data and results of the study. To the President of Universities and State colleges, they should present the concept of the paper for reference for the implementation of productive and sustainable IGPs. To the Human Resource unit, they should improve and develop the aspect of IGPs; instead of treating IGPs as organizations, they should be managed and act like a business entity. To the Universities and State Colleges Income generating Offices, they should promote community products and local crops to empower and emphasize the agriculture sector, which plays a significant role in generating funds.

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